

CROP CALENDAR MAPPING FOR AWD ASSESSMENT OVER BANGLADESH WITH MODIS TIME SERIES FROM 2001-2016

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ABSTRACT: Alternate wetting and drying irrigation system is a less water use and methane emission reduction techniques to allow rice field dry for certain periods. The main objectives of this study to prepare a crop calendar for AWD irrigation appraisal. The important things for crop calendar mapping for AWD assessment are - to monitoring the crop growth and the daily water coverage. In this study, the MODIS satellite images derived NDVI, NDWI and NDSI time series data set from 2001-2017 have been used for spatiotemporal analysis of crop phenology and water coverage. The MODIS 16 day's composite data analysis with Kalman filtered to avoid the cloud contamination and better NDVI, NDWI and NDSI value. The crop calendar assessment refers to observe the crops phenology development from the plantation to harvesting date. The results show the long-term NDVI changes from single fold to multiple folds and NDWI signature shows the positive response to NDVI changes. The cross combination of NDVI, NDWI and NDSI shows a relationship to identify the rice crop area and the NDVI fold helps to detect the crops growing season. The important subject for detecting the AWD irrigation is to detect the irrigated rice crop area because in rain-fed rice cultivation AWD irrigation is not applicable. By using long time MODIS NDVI NDWI and NDSI indices analysis, the crops growing session, change of intensity and seasonal NDVI peak are considered for assessment of crop calendar. The significance of this long-term crop calendar mapping is to analysis the AWD irrigation suitability and evaluating in terms of socioeconomic and environmental benefit. Bangladesh has been selected as a study area, due to the high cropping intensity, 4th largest rice producing country and climate change vulnerability.

KEY WORDS: Alternate Wetting and Drying (AWD), Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), NDWI, Kalman Filter, Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS), Bangladesh

1. INTRODUCTION

Bangladesh is an agricultural country with a very high cropping intensity and diverse crop cultivating country. Almost, 70% of the territory dominant by agriculture land (World Bank, 2014). Bangladesh is the 4th largest per head rice consuming and rice producing country in the world (FAO, 2015). The rice is the dominant crop of the country and it covers three-fourths of all cropland area and contributes 70% of calories consumed (Majumder et al. 2016). Rice is the staple food for more of the half of world population and rice production sector is the largest consumers of irrigational water (GRiSP, 2013). Due to the drastic population growth, the country demanded more rice production in future. But the arable land area of the country is even decreasing over time due to increasing demand for residential and industrial use (Hasan et al., 2013). Bangladesh also suffers from periodic natural calamities such as drought, flooding, and cyclones. Due to its location in a delta, climate change and associated sea level rise are expected to increase the risk for flooding and salinization of agricultural lands, especially near the southern coast (Hossain and Silva, 2013; MOA-FAO, 2012). Due to the primitive laborious agricultural system and lack of proper information on crop monitoring, each and every year country faces a great damaged of crops especially rice paddy crop. The rice cultivated areas of Bangladesh is located low-land, flat and inundate areas and these areas are easily damaged by natural disaster

likes floods, drought and storms. Moreover, rice paddy cultivating consumed huge irrigated groundwater and produce global warming gases especially methane. Alternate wetting and drying technology have been applied for the rice paddy irrigation system to reduce crop water use and methane emission reduction.

AWD irrigation is a great advantage of socio-economic and environmental perspective but still not widely used. To introduce AWD irrigation it's very important to consider the crop growing environment especially the entire growing season. Rice crop calendar especially the showing date is also very important to monitor the crop's development and protected the rice paddy damaged from such natural hazards (Zhao, H., et al., 2009). The main objectives of this paper have been selected the crop calendar assessment for AWD irrigation for rice paddy cultivation. To assess the AWD irrigation system, the irrigated rice areas and rice phenology monitoring are very important. The application of remote sensing is the most advance techniques for monitoring crops phenomena. Remote sensing is the most effective and familiar tools for crops monitoring. Among the remote sensing satellites, the Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectro-radiometer (MODIS) is most promising since its daily repeated cycles and free access to the raw and processed data. The time-series data of the normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) and the enhanced vegetation index (EVI) are the most commonly used remote sensing data (Jiang, Z; et al., 2008). Bangladesh

agricultural diversity and intensity are very high and crop calendar identification is also challenging. The numbers of study have been performed on monitoring crops using MODIS maximum value composite time series data (Sarker *et al.*, 2015; Gumma, *et al.*, 2014; Pei *et al.*, 2006; Rizzi *et al.*, 2006). Moreover, the atmospheric noise components such as clouds, AOD makes its more challenging. In this study kalman filter have been used for avoid of the atmospheric noise. In this paper, the main objective has been fixed to assessment of crop calendar for AWD irrigation with long term MODIS NDVI, NDWI and NDSI analysis.

2.2: Kalman Filter: Kalman filter (Kalman, 1960) is one of the most popular optimal sequential data assimilation algorithms for dynamics and measurement process with Gaussian errors statistics. In this study, a Kalman filter recursive algorithms have been used for to simulate smooth NDVI, NDWI, and NDSI images and estimated their uncertainties at spatial resolution and 16 days time steps. In figure-1 shows the NDVI spectral signature with and without Kalman filter.

Figure-2: With and Without Kalman Filter

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Data: The 16 days composite MODIS MOD13A2 dataset from 2001 to 2017 has been used as a main data source. It's consists of bands 1 (red), 2 (near-infrared), 3 (blue) and 7 (mid-infrared). Rice paddy map produced by Bangladesh Agriculture Research Centre (BARC) has been used as based map for this study. In figure-1 shows the RGB images of NDVI.

Figure-1: RGB Image of Bangladesh

2.3 NDVI, NDWI and NDSI: The present study has used the normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) (Tucker *et al.* 2001). The changes of NDVI indices show the crop growing seasons and it has a different response on various types of LULC classes. The formula follows as-

$$NDVI = (Pnir - Pvis)/(Pnir + Pvis).....(1)$$

Here *Pnir - Pvis* are spectral responses of the pixel in near infrared and visible red bands.

The normalized difference water index is used as a corresponding index of NDVI. The crop patterns especially rice paddy crop shows a positive response with NDVI changes. The simplified formula for NDWI (Filella, *et al.*, 2004) is follows a below formul-2

$$NDWI = (Xgreen - Xnir)/(Xgreen + Xnir).....(2)$$

Where *Xgreen* refers to the green band (MODIS band 4) and *Xnir* refers to the nir band (MODIS band 2). Although NDSI index is more effectives for snow detection but it also have a positive values to the soil surface coverage. The formula for NDSI is as follow-

$$NDSI = (SWIR-NIR)/(SWIR+NIR).....(3) (Takeuchi, *et al.* 2004)$$

The research methodology includes data collection, data analysis and representation through various visualization methods. The MODIS images of 2001-2017 time series analysis. The BARC rice paddy map of Bangladesh used as a base map and select some region of interest with rice

paddy cultivating areas. From ROI, the pixel values are calculated and extract the spectral signatures of the indices and compare within time series. The flowchart of research methodology shown in figure-3

Figure-3: Flowchart of Research Methodology

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Crop Calendar detection: To achieves the research objectives the NDVI, NDWI and NDSI values composite in a single graph and it shows that the NDVI values is fluctuating with the NDWI and NDSI values. It's assumed that, when the NDVI is high than the NDWI values also high but the NDSI values shows the negative relation and it's the rice NDVI peak values. The

relationship among NDVI, NDWI and NDSI changes maintain a relationship with the changes of time. The crop calendar of Bangladesh is very complicated due to the land fragmentation and the favourable condition of crop production. The long term time series analysis is the best way to get a clear idea about the crop calendar. The rice paddy is produce under the flooded condition. To detect the rice calendar long term NDVI is analysis with NDWI and NDSI. The NDWI have a good relation with flooding condition and the condition and NDSI interact with the fallow season. In figure-4, is shows the indices relationship from 2001-2017 in a rice crop region of interest.

3.2: Crop Calendar to AWD: Crop calendar especially rice crop calendar refers the total crop growing season from planting to harvesting in different season. In Bangladesh, the planting and harvesting dates are differ from region to region even farmer to farmer. In this case it's very tough to detect the crop calendar. With the long term MODIS NDVI analysis, the rice growing season NDVI and the intensity of rice growing season considered for the irrigated rice area detection. According the experienced farmer and agricultural officers, generally the rice growing season follows 2:1 ratio for the highest peak of NDVI. Within the two-third days of total growing season the rice paddy reached to the high growth stages and rest of the times takes for flowering and harvesting. The 2:1 ratio is considered for the NDVI peak detection in this study. The long time NDVI analysis shows the NDVI peak in single, double or triple fold and it's indicated the rice growing season or calendar. After detect the rice paddy and peak of NDVI, the AWD irrigation detection is another challenging tusk. The traditional rice is grow in flooded condition but AWD irrigated rice is grown under periodic wetting and drying condition and within the irrigated rice paddy area the AWD irrigated rice paddy is located. The figure-5 shows the rice crop calendar in Bangladesh under irrigate rice cultivated areas.

Figure-4: NDVI, NDWI and NDSI values of Crop area

Figure-5: Annual rice crop calendar

3.3 NDVI and Rice Crop Calendar: The long term NDVI and other indices relationship with NDVI are determined the rice crop area over Bangladesh. From the long-term NDVI and the 2:1 ratio of peak NDVI are showing the figure-6. In Bangladesh, the NDVI values are increasing over the time. Due to the irrigation facilities development the gross area under rice crop have been increased. The statistics and the relevant research work also proved the result. Moreover, the cropping intensity also increased over the time. The single rice crop area to double rice and even triple rice crop areas has found in the country.

Figure-6: Long-term NDVI and Rice Calendar

4. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE OUTLINE

Crop calendar analysis for AWD irrigation is critically evaluated in this study. Crop calendar and AWD irrigation identification is depends on a numbers of parameter. To get an accurate result, it's essential to analysis other parameter also. The MODIS NDVI, NDWI and NDSI indexes show a good signature to identified crop calendar and AWD irrigation rice paddy. In next step, long term Land surface soil water coverage and daily precipitation data will be analysis and calibrated with MODIS long term NDVI indices.

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